

A human-in-the-loop approach for enhancing mobile robot navigation in presence of obstacles not detected by the sensory set

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Abstract—Human-in-the-loop approaches can greatly enhance human-robot interaction by making the user an active part of the control loop in all those situations where safety is of utmost concern, such as in assistive scenario. This study aims to realize a human-in-the-loop approach, where the human can provide a feedback to a smart wheelchair, to augment its artificial sensory set, improving its capabilities to detect and avoid obstacles. The feedback is recorded by both a keyboard and a brain-computer interface: with this scope, the work has also included a protocol design phase to elicit and evoke human brain event-related potentials. The whole architecture has been validated within a simulated robotic environment, with electroencephalography signals acquired from different test subjects.

Index Terms—Human-In-The-Loop Approach, Robot Navigation, Obstacle Avoidance, BCI, EEG Signals

I. INTRODUCTION

An emerging requirement in Human-Robot Interaction (HRI) is that of effectively using the feedback from the human operator to modify the robot behaviour in all those situations where it can increase safety. This is especially the case of physically assistive robots, which provide mobility to the user, such as smart wheelchairs, which are specialized types of mobile robots, whose main goal is to reach a target safely and accurately together with the user [1]. With this scope, the mobile robot relies on a navigation stack which exploits available maps as well as the information provided by proprioceptive and exteroceptive sensors [2], required at local level to avoid obstacles. Common errors during navigation are represented by unexpected environmental conditions, algorithmic errors or wrong sensor readings. There are several devices which can be used to provide feedback to a robotic platform. In the last years, HRI supported by Brain-Computer Interface (BCI) has emerged as a research topic to allow the user to supervise different robot tasks [3], [4]–[6]. To the best of the authors' knowledge, the problem of obstacle avoidance via EEG signals during navigation of a mobile robot is thus still open [5], [7]. Indeed, the proposed work would contribute to the literature by providing a method to integrate the navigation stack with an external trigger, in order to deal with obstacles, which are not correctly detected. The main aspects, here investigated, regard:

- a human-in-the-loop approach, where the human can provide a feedback in order to augment the artificial robot sensory set and improve specific obstacles detection;

- a method to update the robot navigation stack, used in robotic navigation, when the human feedback is received;
- a way to generate the human feedback by means of a BCI, based on a protocol to elicit the Event-Related Potentials (ERPs) when an obstacle, not detected by the robot sensory set, is sensed by the human operator [8].

The study is focused on a smart wheelchair, which can navigate indoor, avoiding possible obstacles by using only the sensors and intelligence mounted on board. A feedback from the human operator is triggered whenever he/she senses an obstacle, not detected by the robot sensory set. The robot navigation stack is then modified to receive human feedback and generate a virtual obstacle, whose effect is to change the robot local trajectory planner, in order to avoid the obstacle. A BCI is chosen as feedback interface and the protocol to elicit the ERP signal in presence of obstacles is designed. The overall architecture has been firstly tested by using a keyboard, with the aim to validate the baseline performances and then, the results with the BCI classifier are shown. The proposed paper is an extracted of the work published in [9].

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The proposed approach aims to engage the user in the robot navigation loop. The human feedback is used to create a virtual obstacle within the virtual representation built by the robot through its sensory set. In this way the robot local trajectory planner, which can not distinguish between the real and virtual obstacle, modifies the robot trajectory to avoid it. The feedback is physically generated through a BCI system interface and the designed protocol that can evoke ERPs is presented.

Three tasks were defined: the first two are focused on robot navigation, and the last one is focused on ERPs detection. In each task the user was asked to press a keyboard key whenever he/she recognized the presence of an obstacle (i.e., a hole):

- 1) The first involves the user watching the screen where the smart wheelchair navigates, for 5 times, around 10 holes placed in a virtual environment.
- 2) The second involves the user watching the mobile robot that randomly crosses the obstacles from different starting points around the hole for 32 times.
- 3) The third involves the user being asked to equip the BCI system and press a keyboard key whenever he/she

perceives the wheelchair is passing through a hole or is avoiding the obstacle.

The first two tasks were designed to evaluate the accuracy in estimating the positions of the real obstacles. The estimated coordinates are used to place virtual obstacles on the map reconstructed by the robot sensory set and modify its trajectory accordingly. The addition of the third task permits to validate the feasibility of the proposed human-in-the-loop approach when a BCI is used as input device. This task was realized for training the classifier of the BCI system in order to recognize the ERP as a trigger to the adopted framework, where the errors are related to the presence of undetected obstacles on the robot path. The overall flowchart is described in Fig.1.

Fig. 1. Flowchart of the implemented algorithm from receiving a trigger to the obstacles-coordinate estimation and ending with new path-planning.

A. Hardware, software, simulation environment description

Environmental data, acquired for the robot navigation and path planning are managed by the ROS packages in the virtual environment of Gazebo, where the smart wheelchair movement and the acquisition of all the sensors have been recreated. The dedicated ROS package to visualize the robot sensors and state is Rviz. The experiments were conducted in simulation to test the communication among the different algorithms and the involved systems. The mobile robot is able to navigate autonomously acquiring environmental data for path planning, by means of external sensors such as the Hokuyo URG-04LX Laser Rangefinder, the IMU unit and two cameras.

B. Path planning and obstacle detection

In ROS, it is possible to modify the robot's path planning by fusing the sensor's data. Authors have designed a node that estimates the obstacle coordinates on the map, representing it as a virtual object and converting it into a point cloud. Once the trigger is true (i.e., 1) the node retrieves the current robot pose and extracts the X and Y coordinates, as well as the orientation angle θ , and estimates the obstacle position (based on the nature of the trigger event and robot pose) within 2 meters. The estimated coordinates of the hole are calculated based on the robot pose on the map through Eqs. (1)-(2):

$$X.holes = X.robot + S \times \cos(\theta) \quad (1)$$

$$Y.holes = Y.robot + S \times \sin(\theta) \quad (2)$$

where $X.robot$, $Y.robot$, and θ are obtained from listening to the robot pose, which returns in form of quaternions [10], and S refers to the hole distance, since the camera has been oriented to be centered 2 meters away in the space in front of the wheelchair. The θ value is calculated as in Eqs. (3)-(4):

$$\theta = 2 \cdot \text{atan2} \left(\sqrt{q_i^2 + q_j^2 + q_k^2}, q_r \right) \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{q} = q_r + q_i \mathbf{i} + q_j \mathbf{j} + q_k \mathbf{k} \quad (4)$$

where the quantities q_r, q_i, q_j, q_k , are real numbers, and i, j, k are unit-vectors pointing along the three spatial axes in the map frame. The (X, Y) data, used as the center for the obstacle position (i.e., the hole), is then sent to the function that uses ROS Point Cloud Library (PCL) to create a virtual 3D cylinder. The information about the created virtual obstacle is used for two purposes by two different packages: one visualizes in Rviz the point cloud creating a virtual object, while the ROS navigation stack, that executes the robot path planning, receives the virtual obstacles information through point-cloud sensor data and uses this to update the map in order to correct the navigation. This package receives information from odometry and sensors to process these data and then executes commands on mobile base.

C. BCI Protocol

The designed protocol aims to evoke ERPs defined as cognitive responses, elicited when the user reacts to unexpected sensory stimuli. The ERP elicited after a user's recognition of a task error is called Error-Related Potential (ErrP) [11]. The ErrP is generated when a subject commits or observes an error [12], and this aspect is of interest for its integration in a control loop for BCI systems. The proposed protocol is designed based on the "oddball paradigm" [13] with the aim of evoking ERPs, connected with error performance activities and presented as different visual stimuli with the presence or not of obstacles on the robot path planning. The task is consisting of 200 trials of short videos of robot navigation, in presence of obstacles. The 80% of these trials show the robot smoothly navigating successfully avoiding a correctly detected obstacle by turning left or right. The remaining 20% of the trials represents when

the robot collides with an obstacle (e.g., a small hole on the floor). The 200 trials are divided into four groups, each group contains 50 trials presented in a video of 7 minutes, for a maximum session duration of 30 minutes. The user, while seeing the video stream, is asked to press a specific key on the keyboard whenever he/she recognizes that the robot is going to pass through the hole or not. The simulated wheelchair may respect the directional cue, turning left (or right), thus avoiding the hole (correct trial, ‘Turn’), or it may go straight, passing above the hole (non-correct trial, ‘Pass’). The evoked potential has been obtained by filtering the epoched signal by keeping only theta-band through the band-pass filter in range 3–8 Hz.

D. BCI and EEG signal pre-processing

The population involved in the study is composed by 10 healthy subjects whose mean age is 28 years (Standard Deviation (STD) ± 3 years). The BCI2000 software with G.tecg.MobilabPlus DAQ and an actiCAP system has been used for the EEG signals acquisition [14]. 8 channels were placed on the subject’s scalp and the electrodes were arranged according to the international 10/20 system and placed at Fz Cz Po7 P3 Pz P4 Po8 AF8. The data were recorded with a sampling rate of 256 Hz and band-pass filtering is applied between 0.5 and 30 Hz. Afterward, EEG data have been filtered again by a bandpass forward-backward filtering between 1 and 10 Hz (Butterworth second order filter), applied followed by decimation of a factor 8, introducing downsampling from 256 Hz to 32 Hz. The signals are further filtered in different bandwidths and the best one in terms of classification accuracy, 2–5 Hz, is selected for ERPs detection [15]. A Bayesian Linear Discriminant Analysis (BLDA)-based classifier is considered to predict two groups, i.e., ‘Turn’ or ‘Pass’. The data collected from each subject has been divided into 60% for training, and 40% for testing. The implemented algorithm to identify the target task (when the robot does not detect obstacles) works on time windows of 1 second during which the EEG potentials could be detected. When the target event of committing an error is identified by the classifier, it will rise a flag to MATLAB Simulink which will send a trigger to the ROS node.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The robot navigation stack has been modified to receive the feedback from the user through an input device (e.g. keyboard and BCI). When the trigger is received, a virtual obstacle is generated and placed on the robot virtual map, centered on the coordinates estimated via Eqs. (1) to (4). The local trajectory planner of the robot is affected by the virtual obstacle and avoids the real obstacle as long as its position is close to the estimated one. Authors present the results obtained for estimating the obstacles’ positions in a simulation environment, when the trigger is generated and those obtained by using the BCI protocol in terms of ERP classification. The users are sitting in front of the screen and have to press a keyboard key, when they see an obstacle, centred on the screen, during the real-time robot navigation. The main statistical indexes related to the estimation errors,

related to the 5 trials of the first task, are reported in Table I. The estimated position is calculated by the Eqs. (1), (2), (3), (4) when the user generates the trigger with the keyboard. In robotics, obstacle avoidance is commonly performed by considering the obstacle area increased by a safety threshold, namely the inflation radius. If the error between the estimated position of the obstacle and the real one is less than the inflation radius, the center of the virtual obstacle will fall within the inflated area of the real one and viceversa.

TABLE I

TASK 1: STATISTICAL INDEXES OF THE ESTIMATION ERRORS IN THE POSITIONS OF THE OBSTACLES.

Error	Value	Unit
Average	0.21	m
Min	0.03	m
Max	0.64	m
Standard-deviation	0.12	m
Variance	0.02	m ²

During the navigation through the obstacles test, the wheelchair randomly crosses a single obstacle from 32 different starting points. Depending on the approaching direction, the trigger from the user can be generated before or after the hole, thus the virtual obstacle can be centered before or after the real one. Table II, again, resumes the main statistical indexes related to the estimation errors. Resuming

TABLE II

TASK 2: STATISTICAL INDEXES OF THE ESTIMATION ERRORS IN THE POSITIONS OF THE OBSTACLES.

Error	Value	Unit
Average	0.30	m
Min	0.02	m
Max	0.75	m
Standard-deviation	0.178	m
Variance	0.02	m ²

the presented data, it is possible to notice that in Table I, the maximum error reported is 0.64 m, while in Table II is of 0.75 m. The two values are both greater than the accepted error threshold of 0.50 m. Differently, the average error is 0.21 m for the first task and 0.30 for the second one: both are small and represent an estimation accuracy which falls within the threshold of the inflation radius. The minimum error reported in the two tables is of 0.03 m in Table I and of 0.02 m in Table II. The precision can be evaluated by considering the standard deviations, namely 0.12 m for the first and 0.178 m for the second. Moreover, the results related to the ERP detection for the human-in-the-loop control feedback are shown through the Area Under the Curve (AUC) of the Receiver-Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve [16]. Good AUC values range from 0.5 to 1, the latter meaning perfect classification of elements belonging to both positive and negative classes. Table III shows the results of offline ERPs detection, obtained considering a time window of 1 second (i.e., 1 second from ‘Time 0’ and all channels for classification). EEG signals are filtered considering the bandwidth of 2-5 Hz, exploited for

classification due to its best performance in terms of AUC. Subject 2 shows the best result in terms of AUC both for training and testing.

TABLE III
AUC INDEX OF ERPS DETECTION OBTAINED FROM 10 HEALTHY SUBJECTS.

Subject	AUCtrain	AUCtest
S001	0.85	0.61
S002	0.96	0.72
S003	0.73	0.53
S004	0.63	0.51
S005	0.64	0.54
S006	0.61	0.55
S007	0.73	0.66
S008	0.73	0.62
S009	0.69	0.53
S010	0.55	0.45
means	0.73	0.59
std	0.11	0.07

Fig. 2. Grand average over Fz channel for two conditions, 'Pass' and 'Turn'.

In Fig. 2 the ErrPs grand average morphology, generated when the user recognizes the robot is going to pass through the hole (non-correcting trial) has been analyzed to highlight the differences between the two conditions 'Pass' and 'Turn'.

IV. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

The proposed study has presented a method to integrate the navigation realized by a mobile robot, equipped with onboard sensors, with a human feedback, provided by both a keyboard and a brain-computer interface. For this purpose, the work includes also a protocol design phase to elicit ERPs potentials. The obtained results support the strategy of using virtual obstacles for mobile robot trajectory correction through visible and applicable point cloud objects giving good accuracy and precision about the exact negative obstacle's position (i.e., holes in the ground). Among the advantages of this approach, there is a reduced computational request. The human feedback has been generated through a BCI. The ERPs elicited after the user recognizes a task error are defined as ErrPs. Through a BLDA classifier, considered for the binary classification, the evoked signals have been classified into two groups ('Turn' and 'Pass'). The virtual obstacle has a fixed size regardless of the detected real obstacle size, and this will require further improvements in the future. Some disadvantages of the proposed

approach are related to the ERP detection which is not quite good for some subjects. Moreover, the training of the data analysis algorithm is time demanding and subject-dependent. The proposed BCI protocol is synchronous, thus a possible future research direction could be the investigation and the introduction of asynchronous protocols in the framework in order to test more realistic scenarios.

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